

INFORMATION, COMMUNICATION AND TECHNOLOGY (ICT) IS FOR TEACHER AND STUDENT

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ABSTRACT

In the article it is observed that Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) is the type of technology employed in the shape of tools, equipment and application support, that helps in the collection, storage, retrieval, use, transmission, manipulation and dissemination of information as accurately and efficiently as possible. It is for the purpose of enriching the knowledge and developing communication, decision making as well as problem solving ability of the user.

ICT will not only include hardware devices connected to computers, and software applications, but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web based content repositories, interactive forums, learning management systems, and management information systems.

These will also include processes for digitisation, deployment and management of content, development and deployment of platforms and processes for capacity development, and creation of forums for interaction and exchange.

Benefits of ICT to teachers, Teachers most often use ICTs for 'routine tasks' (record keeping, lesson plan development, information presentation, basic information searches on the Internet). Teachers more knowledgeable in ICTs use utilize computer-assisted instruction less

than other teachers who use ICTs, but utilize ICTs more overall.

ICT helps teachers to interact with students. It helps them in preparation their teaching, provide feedback. ICT also helps teachers to access with institutions and Universities, NCERT, NAAC NCTE and UGC etc. It also helps in effective use of ICT software and hardware for teaching – learning process.

Steps to Integrate ICT in Education

- Develop an appreciation of where the children are. ...
- Plan and seek to develop all components of ICT capability. ...
- Embed ICT in the meaningful and purpose-driven context. ...
- Select the appropriate ICT tools. ...
- Practice formative assessment strategies throughout the year.

Importance of ICT in Education and Teaching-Learning Process:

ICT plays the same role in our information and communication process and their outcomes, as played by other technologies in making our life comfortable and purposeful. ICT in education has tremendous potential to serve and help the people connected with the process and product of education in many ways.

1. ICT can bring the existing educational system in alignment with the knowledge-based, information-rich society by providing services of sophisticated tools, techniques and methods at its disposal.

2. Use of ICT can bring about a paradigm shift in traditional views and methods of teaching — learning process. Some of the changes are as follows:

a. It will help in transitioning from a broadcast model of learning to interactive learning. Thus making the students active and participate in the teaching — learning process.

b. Helps in the process of transitioning from teacher-centered instruction to learner-centered instruction. Students become self-reliant and self-directed in acquisition and application of knowledge and skills

c. Shifts emphasis from teaching to learning thereby creating a more interactive and engaging learning environment for both teachers and students.

d. Changes the role of teachers from a mere knowledge-transmitter to that of a learning-facilitator, knowledge guide or navigator and an active co-learner along with students.

e. Enables students to become more responsible about their learning as they seek out relevant information and knowledge through their own efforts, synthesize and share their knowledge with

others. It makes them realize their educational potentials.

f. ICT helps students to think critically and creatively and to reflect on their own learning process. They even set their individual goals for growth and development of their potentials.

3. ICT prepares teachers to meet challenges of the teaching-learning task of modern age. It helps teachers in proper execution of their multi-dimensional responsibilities in various areas of education.

4. ICT can be beneficial not only to teachers for their own education and training but also to use it creatively for accelerating the educational growth of their students.

5. Schools or Students that have no access to computer devices like PCs, laptops, tablets or smartphones can especially utilize ICT in the form of Radiobroadcasts and Telecast. There are specific educational programs such as Gyanvani and Gyandarshan hosted by Akashvani and Doordarshan respectively to cater to the subjects of a school curriculum.

For such students, traditional ICT tools such as pictures, charts, models, graphs, blackboard, newspapers, educational visits, excursions or educational fairs and exhibitions can be utilized for learning and applying school subjects.

6. In schools, or students that have access to computer but no internet connection –

a. pre-recorded CDs and DVDs containing useful content may be used.

b. Various word processing programs such as MS word can be used by both teachers and students alike. Teachers can prepare their lesson plans, write Questionnaire, prepare evaluations and diagnostic test to check performance of the students. Students can make their assignments using

MS Word using creative designs and templates.

c. MS Excel can be used by teachers in middle and primary school for data collection, analysis and presentation. It is especially important in teaching students the im

portance of data collection and representation in the form of — Bar graphs, pie charts, histograms etc.

d. Power point presentations can be prepared by teachers as well as students using the MS PowerPoint Application to present and demonstrate their lessons in effective and efficient manner.

e. Interactive whiteboards (IWB) also known as smartboards are electronic and digital boards that help in showing what's presented on a computer desktop with the help of a projector. It helps to control the computer with the help of a pen to conduct a lecture in an interactive manner.

f. Software such as Interactive Geometry software, Instructional Software, Simulation, gaming and recreational software provides for rich alternative source for teaching and learning. They can help to remove fear and phobias related to study of a subject at the same time providing them opportunities to learn while playing or engaging in virtual applications of the principles and processes of a subject.

An intelligent software while interacting with students in its tutorial may tell where an error was made on the part of the. Student while solving problems and offer suggestions for reaching a. correct answer based specifically on the students incorrect answer.

7. In case of students who have computer services in school with internet facilities,

the amount of information available to them is immeasurable.

a. World wide web (WWW) is updating the knowledge warehouses for students, teachers, scientist due to enormous progress of ICT. Anybody can refer the latest information and research every day.

b. Open universities and distance education through ICT are new openings for working people to acquire, knowledge to study at home also.

ICT can be useful for a teacher in the following ways:

1. It is helpful in the professional development of the teachers. A teacher can learn various language skills with the help of ICT. They can do various certification programs run by the famous educational institutions like Cambridge University, British Council etc. These programs help in enhancing his capacity to teach his subject content easy, economic and more understandable.

2. A teacher can increase his domain of knowledge with the help of e-journals, e-magazines and e-library that can be achieved only through the use of ICT. He can also participate in discussions and conferences with the experts of his subject teaching to improve his knowledge and skills through audio and video conferencing.

3. ICT helps a teacher to learn innovative methods of teaching. He can work with the students on various project and assignments. It also helps him in providing teaching contents, home works etc.

4. He may participate in various in-service training programs and workshops which are essential for his professional development with the help of ICT.

5. ICT helps a teacher to guide his students about the learning materials available on

internet, e-books, e-journals, e-magazines and social sites like linked –in which are helpful in better learning of subject skills.

6. ICT also helps him framing curriculum of subjects. He can study curriculums of different countries to study their pros and cons, challenges as well as sociological and psychological issues related to learners. All these things help him in framing a curriculum that leads to achieve the aims and objectives of subject of teaching.

ICT can be useful for a student in the following ways:

1. Student can study through online resources. There are different resources through which it will be helpful for students to understand topic. Students can learn from their place and at any time.
2. Students can meet teachers online and get required knowledge about the subject.
3. Students can have no limit of time and place.

In this way there are different apps through which teaching learning process is becoming more easy. These apps help teachers and students to communicate with each other and get knowledge of particular subject. Teachers are also learning different apps use for teaching and students are using for learning process. In this way ICT tools are helpful in this pandemic situation. These tools are helping teachers as well as students.

Due to Covid-19, there is no option without online education. As lockdowns don't allow to open schools, colleges, so online education is only one option through which education can be continued.

Different apps nowadays are used for online education. These apps are helpful for students and teachers to reach. Such type of apps are also used for meetings, online teaching learning process. Ex. Zoom, Google meet, Webex etc. There are different platforms available for online education. Through these platforms, online classes can be taken, videos can be uploaded, recorded videos can be send. So these platforms are helpful to the students as well as teachers. Ex. Swayam, Webex, Impartus etc. Due to online education there is no time limit as well as place restriction for learning. Anyone can learn from any place and at any time. So many type of education any one can take. And different e-contents are also prepared for students. These are helpful for them to enrich their knowledge. GeoGebra can construct almost every conceivable geometrical object, even in 3D! Object drawing is interactive and can be moved around, modified, measured. PhET Simulations are interactive computer programs which allow a user to change variables and see the effect of the changes on the system. These are very useful in helping students explore the subject, solve problems and can also become a useful self-assessment tool. Using a tool or creating a tool calls for a clear view of the end result — the exact task to be accomplished. Working back from this, the ability to understand the process or procedure of accomplishing the task together with the skill to wield the tool is to be gained. Therein lies the challenge. Therein lies the fascination.

References:

1. Learning and Teaching, S K Mangal and. Shubhra Mangal
2. National Policy on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) In School Education

3. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/revised_policy%20document%20ofICT.pdf
4. E-Pathshala: <https://epathshala.nic.in/epathshala.php?ln=en>
5. The National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER) : <https://nroer.gov.in/welcome>
6. Swayam: <https://swayam.gov.in/explorer>
7. Swayam Prabha: <https://www.swayamprabha.gov.in/>